

Relationship between Foreign Direct Investment and Export in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between exports and foreign direct investment and the real exchange rate in the case of Sri Lanka, employing a correlation and regression approach to the data ranging from 1977 to 2021. The coefficient for LnFDI inflow is 0.1279 and was significant. This means that for every 1% increase in FDI, exports will increase by 0.1278 %. The Real Exchange Rate is also positively related to exports of Sri Lanka. The coefficient for LnReeR is 0.9296 and was significant. This indicates that for every 1% change in real exchange rate, exports will change by 0.9296 %. Both variables are strongly related and move in the same direction and explain the changes in Sri Lankan exports. This present study reveals that Sri Lankan exports are positively interrelated and the relationship is complementary. The findings also indicate that foreign direct investment and Real Exchange rate are key determinants of Sri Lankan exports. It is recommended that the government and policymakers engage in FDI diversification to expand the export base of Sri Lanka.

Keywords: FDI, Export, Real Exchange Rate, Sri Lanka.

Introduction

Foreign direct investment (FDI) refers to direct investment flows in an economy. It is the sum of equity capital, reinvestment of earnings, and other capital. Direct investment is a category of cross-border investment associated with a resident in one economy having control or a significant degree of influence on the management of an enterprise that is resident in another economy. FDI and international trade are drivers of the global economy. It facilitates the cross-border transfer of goods, services, and capital around the world. FDI and trade have become increasingly interrelated in today's global economy with the emergence of multinational firms. As stated by Fontagne (1999), the interaction between trade and FDI is a main feature of globalization. International trade and FDI have been playing more and more important roles in the world economy. FDI refers to an investment in or the acquisition of foreign assets with the intent to control and manage them. Businesses can make an FDI in several ways, including purchasing the assets of a foreign business, investing in the company or in new property, plants, or equipment or participating in a joint venture with a foreign business. The overall aim of this study is to attempt to understand the relationship between export Foreign Direct Investment and the Real exchange rate in Sri Lanka.

Literature Review

Silva (2011) studied Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in the Context of Trade and Economic Development in Sri Lanka. The study examined the various issues related to FDI definitions, trends, perspectives, policies, and significant operations during the two decades, the decline during the global economic crisis (2007-2009), and prospects for 2010-2011. Sultanuzzaman. et.al (2018) submitted a paper on the role of

FDI inflows and export on economic growth in Sri Lanka: An ARDL approach. This paper examines the long-run and short-run relationship between Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows, exports, and economic growth in Sri Lanka from 1980–2016. The study implies an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach to reveal the relationship between the variables. Another empirical study investigates the determinants of FDI inflows into Sri Lanka using annual data for the period 1978–2013 and applying the latest econometric techniques in time series analysis (Ravinthirakumaran et al, 2015). Abamu & Pietrzak, (2019) investigated the relationship between FDI and international trade from an export perspective in Nigeria. A correlation analysis was performed to determine the relationship between the two variables. Findings show that there is a strong positive relationship between FDI and exports. A regression analysis using OLS showed a very significant relationship between the two and revealed that an increase in FDI causes an increase in the country's exports. Rahman, (2011), carried out an empirical Study on the Relationship between Foreign Investment and International Trade in Bangladesh. The author aims at empirically search the long-run relationship and causality between FDI and trade (export and import) in Bangladesh taking data between 1972 and 2007. Dasha, and Sharma, (2010) investigated the interrelationship between export and Foreign Direct Investment for major South Asian countries, namely India, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka and Pakistan. The study is based on the Granger non-causality test. The evidence shows that there is a bi-directional causality between FDI and Trade. The results of their study indicate a complementary relationship between FDI and Trade. Kang & Lee, (2021) examined the impact of FDI on trade of the East Asian economic transition countries, namely China, Cambodia, Lao PDR, and Vietnam, employing FDI flow and FDI stock data separately.

Method and materials

The empirical analysis presented in this paper is based on a time series data set which were collected in the publications of the Central Bank of Sri Lanka from 1977 to 2021. To examine the relationship of FDI on trade in Sri Lanka. The data series included exports of goods and services as a percentage of the GDP (EXP), the foreign direct investment inflows as a percentage of the GDP (FDI), and the Real exchange rate (REER). Mukhtarov, et al, (2019) investigated the impact of foreign direct investment (FDI) on exports employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bounds Testing (ARDL BT) co-integration approach in Jordan. Abamu and Pietrzak (2019) used a model to find out the relationship between FDI and International Trade in Nigeria. They used a simple linear regression approach to find out the relationship between FDI and Export. The same approach was employed in this study. Referring to the reviewed literature the following regression equation was identified to analyze the relationship between FDI and Export. The log-linear form is considered most appropriate by various empirical studies. This functional form gives elasticity coefficients directly. Moreover, the log-linear form reduces the problem of heteroscedasticity in an empirical analysis. Therefore, empirical results estimated by this model are appropriate for policy implications. For these purposes, all variables are expressed in natural logarithmic form

$$\ln EXP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln FDI_t + \beta_2 \ln REER_t + u_i$$

Where:

- EXP – Exports of goods and services (% of GDP).
- FDI – FDI inflows (% of GDP)
- REER – The real exchange rate.
- β_s – Parameters of the model.
- u – random error.
- t – Time period.

FDI and Export of Sri Lanka

Sri Lanka is a lower-middle-income country in South Asia. The gross domestic product (GDP) was \$84.5 billion and the per capita GDP was \$3,815 in 2021. Sri Lanka receives FDI after the introduction of the liberalization policy in 1977. Sri Lanka received Million US \$ 1,474,392.373 FDI in 1978, whereas it received Rs. 477,559,000 Million US \$ FDI in 2010. FDI into Sri Lanka increased to 597,522,167.7 million US \$ in 2021, in comparison to 433,869,416 million US \$ million in 2020. Presently the FDI was focused on real estate, mixed development projects, ports, and telecommunications sectors. The tourism sector, cultural, wildlife, and outdoor offerings is a priority sector for the government’s economic recovery plan. Therefore, the Sri Lankan government plans to obtain more FDI for these sectors. The government’s economic goals are positioning Sri Lanka as an export-oriented economic hub at the center of the Indian Ocean. However, economists say Sri Lanka has not performed well in attracting foreign direct investment. Liberalizing trade policies by reducing tariffs and other barriers to increase the trade openness. Trade openness can have implications on FDI inflows. The high degree of trade barriers can increase transaction costs for multinationals engaged in vertical FDI (Busse & Hefeker, 2007)

Figure 01 shows the Sri Lankan Export and FDI as a percentage of GDP from 1977 to 2021. Foreign direct investment into Sri Lanka increased to \$784 million in 2021, in comparison to \$670 million in 2020, after decreasing from \$793 million in 2019 and \$1.6 billion in 2018. Recent FDI was concentrated in real estate, mixed development projects, ports, and telecommunications sectors. The tourism sector, with around two million tourist arrivals per year (before the global COVID-19 pandemic) and a variety of cultural, wildlife, and outdoor offerings, is a priority sector for the government’s economic recovery plan

Results and Discussion

Firstly two methods, descriptive statistics and correlation analysis have been applied to verify the model. Descriptive statistics is used to describe the main features of data collection using numerical and graphical methods. In this study table 1 presents the descriptive conditions of FDI Exports and Real Exchange Rate by using the mean, maximum, minimum, and standard deviation values.

Table 1: Descriptive conditions of FDI, Exports and Real Exchange Rate

	Export	FDI	ReeR
Mean	5350.709	35685	79.779
Median	4699.000	19342	70.635
Maximum	12498.60	16140	198.764
Minimum	767.1000	-12185	8.872

SD	3867.602	39304	52.297
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Figure 2 Trends of the Variables

The correlation analysis was to see the co-variation between the variables and also to quantify the relationship strength between the variables. Correlation analysis will test and measure the strength of the relationship between the FDI, Real exchange rate and dependent variable export.

Table 2 Correlation of the Variables

	Export	FDI	REER
Export	1		
FDI	0.888	1	
REER	0.966	0.801	1

results in the correlation matrix above show that the correlation coefficient between FDI and export is 0.888. and the correlation coefficient between export and ReeR is 0.966. This shows a strong positive relationship Export between both other variables.

Table 3 Regression Outputs

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNFDI	0.127923	0.033420	3.827680	0.0004
LNREER	0.929613	0.064373	14.44105	0.0000
C	1.991498	0.415330	4.794974	0.0000
R-squared	0.973847	Mean dependent var	8.281358	
Adjusted R-squared	0.972571	S.D. dependent var	0.882434	
S.E. of regression	0.146146	Akaike info criterion	-0.942680	
Sum squared resid	0.875701	Schwarz criterion	-0.821030	
Log likelihood	23.73895	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-0.897566	
F-statistic	763.3464	Durbin-Watson stat	0.745771	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Using a regression model, the coefficient for LnFDI inflow is 0.1279 and was significant with a p-value of 0.0004. This means that for every 1% increase in FDI, exports will increase by 0.1278 %. The findings as shown above indicate that FDI is a key determinant of exports in Sri Lanka. The present findings support the findings of Abamu. B. E. & Pietrzak. J., (2019), and Okechukwu et al., (2018) found a positive and significant relationship between FDI and exports in Nigeria. Suresh Kumar, (2022) also found a positive relationship between FDI and exports in in India.

The real Exchange rate is also positively related to exports of Sri Lanka. The coefficient for LnReeR is 0.9296 and was significant with a p-value of 0.0000. This indicates that for every 1% change in real exchange rate, exports will change by 0.9296 %. The findings as shown above indicate that real exchange rate is also a key determinant of exports in Sri Lanka. Both variables are strongly related and move in the same direction and explain the changes in exports. Sureshkumar (2022) while studying the impact of FDI on the economy, found that FDI has a positive impact on exports.

Conclusions

This study aimed to examine the relationship between FDI inflows into Sri Lanka and the country's exports. The study achieved this objective using a correlation and regression analysis to test the strength of and estimate the relationship between the two variables. It established that there is a strong and statistically significant relationship between exports and FDI as well as the real exchange rate of Sri Lanka from 1977 to 2021. This present study reveals that Sri Lankan exports are positively interrelated and the relationship is complementary. FDI has long been considered an engine of economic growth in the host countries. One of the channels of accelerating economic growth is through promoting exports. Therefore, it is recommended that the government and policymakers engage in FDI diversification to expand the export base. The government should provide a good environment in the area of security so that foreign investors would be encouraged to invest more in the country.

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